

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF DEVIANT BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE

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Abstract

The article analyzes sociological approaches to the analysis of deviations and deviant behavior. The sociocultural aspect of deviations and deviant behavior of adolescents is considered. Forms defined deviations among adolescents in modern conditions.

Keywords: Deviation, deviant behavior, forms of deviant behavior, prevention.

From experience of working with adolescent children, as well as the results of psychodiagnostic examinations of this age category, the following frequently encountered behavioral deviations can be identified and defined:

- Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD);
- Verbal and nonverbal aggression;
- Insecure behavior;
- Peer rivalry;
- Skipping classes.

To prevent negative consequences in adolescent behavior, it is necessary to identify the psychological causes of the corresponding deviations and determine the methods for their solution. Based on this, two parameters were proposed: adequacy and timeliness, ensuring the effectiveness of practical psychologists in solving the corresponding psychological problems [4].

Adequacy includes the quantity and quality of data used by the psychologist in the process of examining the given problem; determination of methods for solving the corresponding problems and the accuracy of identifying the psychological causes of deviations. In order for these parameters to be effective in solving certain problems in psychological work, the work should be structured correctly, starting from the first stages, since with incorrectly identified psychological causes of deviations in the behavior of adolescents, it is difficult to achieve a positive result. For this reason, the correctness of the definition (adequacy) and the timeliness of identifying the main deviations in the behavior of adolescents are undoubtedly important.

A psychologist begins solving psychodiagnostic problems by collecting anamnestic data about a teenager. This work is carried out in the process of intensive interaction with people who have various information about the teenager. These are primarily parents, relatives, and also teachers of educational institutions. Each specialist independently builds a scheme of psychological work at this stage.

Some experts claim that the psychodiagnostic process is based on a descriptive study of consciousness, subjectivity and experiences of a teenager, this is the so-called "phenomenological"

level. At this stage, the request for a problem is studied, data on variable parameters of activity or mental state are collected, and a general picture of the object of psychological diagnostics is drawn up.

Other specialists insist on collecting anamnesis, believing that it is necessary to collect information if there is a real problem. For example, if the problem concerns mental development (poor academic performance, poor memory, inattention, etc.), then possible sources may be organic brain damage, disorders in early mental development [5].

Based on such schemes, we have developed a program for collecting anamnestic data. This program has been tested in the work of a practical psychologist to identify deviations in the behavior of adolescent children.

Program for collecting anamnestic data of adolescents with behavioral deviations

Information received from teachers:

- the teenager's education, starting from the moment he went to school, what difficulties he experienced, in what subjects, in particular, whether there were any and how were there any successes in studies;

- the teenager's behavior in the process of communicating with peers and adults, behavior in lessons, breaks;

- communication problems: communication with relatives, peers, adults;

- problems of the emotional and personal sphere: the teenager's behavior in various life situations (public speaking, writing independent work, doing homework);

- neurological manifestations: fears, tics, increased fatigue, obsessive movements).

Information received from parents:

- the teenager's education, starting with attending kindergarten, then at what age he went to school, whether there were any successes or difficulties in the learning process, how independently he did his homework, as well as information about hobbies (attending clubs, sports sections);

- the teenager's behavior in the family: attitude towards different family members, fulfillment of

requirements, assignments, as well as behavior: communication with parents outside the home (in a store, on the street, when visiting); behavioral features, communication with other children, adults; note which of the parents devotes more time to the child;

- educational aspects: how often and in what cases punishments and rewards are present, whether problems arise in communication, how often communication is of a conflict nature, whether there is a model of education in the family based on the examples of family members;

- emotional and personal problems: manifestation of emotional arousal in various life situations, communication with adults at home, on the street, communication with peers of the opposite sex, the degree of subservience, suggestibility, manifestation of aggression, negativism;

- neurological manifestations: fears, restless sleep, frequent fatigue, tics, enuresis;

- family: composition, complete or incomplete; are there older or younger brothers and sisters;

- health or developmental status at all age periods, as well as: course of pregnancy, childbirth, prematurity, etc.; indicate injuries received, illnesses suffered in the first years, whether there were any consequences; describe the developmental features in the first year of life (speech, walking, etc.);

- education: features of education at school or a vocational institution;

- consultation with a psychologist (appearance, behavioral features of the teenager during the consultation: willingly answers questions or shows aggression, anxiety, stiffness).

In conclusion, it is important to note that the psychological characteristics of adolescence must first be diagnosed. Psychological diagnostics can take place in 2 directions:

- observation and consultation of a psychologist;
- request from parents or teachers.

The program for collecting anamnestic data presented by us has practical significance and can be used by practical psychologists in their work. Obtaining anamnestic data is the very beginning, only the first stage of all psychological work with teenagers, followed by a built, planned psychological program containing certain methods, ways, and techniques[6]. Each specialist independently chooses the scheme for obtaining anamnestic data and carries out his further work.

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doi: 10.1080/01639625.2014.944069.